

Case report

Incidental multiple congenital neck cysts: a case report and review of literature on the simultaneous occurrence of thyroglossal duct and branchial cleft cysts

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Abstract

Background: The simultaneous occurrence of two (2) congenital cystic neck lesions, such as a thyroglossal duct cyst (TGDC) and a branchial cleft cyst (BCC), is extremely rare. They usually present in childhood and early adulthood as painless neck swellings, often not associated with any symptom unless infected or exposed to trauma. While each lesion individually represents a well-documented congenital anomaly, their simultaneous presentation within the same patient poses a unique diagnostic and therapeutic challenge. **Objectives:** To present a case of a 22-year-old man with synchronous thyroglossal duct and branchial cleft cysts. **Case Presentation:** A 22-year-old man presented to our facility with complaints of progressive, painless anterior neck swelling that was noticed since birth. Neck examination revealed an oval-shaped mass in the distal half of the anterior border of the left sternocleidomastoid muscle, with normal overlying skin, which moves with deglutition but not with protrusion of the tongue. It measures 10 x 7 cm, has no differential warmth, is not tender, and is not attached to the overlying skin but is firmly attached to the underlying structures, limiting movement in the horizontal plane. It has a smooth surface, a well-defined edge, and a firm consistency. The trachea deviated to the right. He had an excisional biopsy of the neck mass via Coller's incision, which revealed 2 separate masses. The histological report of the two masses showed features in keeping with thyroglossal duct cyst and branchial cleft cyst, respectively.

Keywords: Branchial cleft cyst, Incidental multiple congenital neck cysts, Thyroglossal duct cyst.

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Introduction

Congenital cystic lesions of the neck are relatively common in otorhinolaryngological practice. Among these, **thyroglossal duct cysts (TGDCs)** and **branchial cleft cysts (BCCs)** are among the most frequently encountered, occurring at a ratio of 3:1, respectively.¹⁻⁷ While TGDCs represent 70% of congenital neck swellings, the second branchial cleft anomalies, which present mostly in the form of cysts or sinuses, are the commonest anomalies of the branchial apparatus accounting for about 90% of cases of branchial apparatus anomalies.¹⁻⁷ Simultaneous occurrence of these congenital neck anomalies is very rare with very few reportable cases in the literature.¹⁻⁷ Here we present the simultaneous occurrence of thyroglossal duct cyst and Branchial cyst in a 22-year Oldman.

Case Presentation

A 22-year-old man presented to our facility with complaints of progressive, painless anterior neck swelling that was noticed since birth. No associated regression or discharge from the swelling, and no associated dysphagia, dyspnoea

or hoarseness. No associated features of hypo or hyperthyroidism. His pregnancy, labour and delivery were all uneventful.

Neck examination revealed an oval-shaped mass in the distal half of the anterior border of the left sternocleidomastoid muscle, with normal overlying skin and no discharging sinus or fistula. It moves with deglutition but not with protrusion of the tongue; it measures 10 x 7 cm, has no differential warmth, not-tender, not attached to the overlying skin but is firmly attached to the underlying structures, limiting movement in horizontal planes. It has a smooth surface, a well-defined edge, a firm consistency, no pulsation, and no thrill or bruit. Berry's and Kocher's signs were negative. The trachea was deviated to the right, with no retrosternal extension. (Figure 1A and 1B) No eye signs. No cervical or supraclavicular lymphadenopathy. Other systemic reviews were essentially normal.

Assessment of a left branchial cyst with differential of thyroid cyst was made.

He had a neck ultrasound scan done, which showed both lobes of the thyroid gland to be normal in size and outline, measuring 1.19 x 1.44 x 2.49 cm and 1.03 x 1.06 x 1.68 cm on the right and left, respectively. The isthmus was normal in outline and echo pattern, measuring 0.19 cm. A well-defined thick-walled lesion with internal echoes within it was seen just below the left lobe of the thyroid gland, displacing the thyroid gland superiorly. It does not show colour flow on Doppler interrogation. An impression of a branchial cyst was made.

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Figure 1: Clinical appearance of the neck swellings

X-ray soft tissue of the neck (anterior-posterior and lateral views) revealed a huge, well-defined mass of soft tissue density at the lower aspect of the anterior neck (corresponding to the level of the C5-C8 cervical vertebrae) compressing and deviating the airway to the right at that level. No calcification was seen within it. The visualized cervical vertebrae, disc spaces, and posterior elements were all normal. An impression of thyroid enlargement was made (Figure 2).

Figure 2: X-ray of soft tissue of the neck (anteroposterior & lateral views)

Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) of the neck mass revealed a hypocellular smear showing few epithelial cells along with numerous siderophages in a haemorrhagic background. No malignant cells seen. An assessment of a benign swelling mass was made. Other investigations done were complete blood count (CBC), Electrolyte, Urea and Creatinine (E/U/Cr), as well as Urinalysis, which were all normal.

He had an excisional biopsy of the neck mass via Coller's incision (transverse skin crease incision 2 finger breaths above the suprasternal notch extending between the posterior borders of the sternocleidomastoid muscle). Intraoperative findings revealed an ovoid, well-encapsulated cystic mass (Mass A – Figure 3A) measuring 9 x 6 x 5 cm in the lower aspect of the left anterior triangle of the neck, compressing the left thyroid lobe but not attached to it, but pushing the trachea to the right. A cystic mass (Mass B – Figure 3B) measuring 2.5 x 2 x 1 cm was seen just above Mass A but more anteriorly placed, with about 1.8 ml of serous fluid within it. The right and left thyroid lobes were all normal.

Figure 3A

Figure 3B

Figure 3C

Figure 3 shows exposure of the operative site after raising a platysmal flap, incision through the investing layer of deep cervical fascia, and retraction of the strap muscles in order to expose the masses adequately.

The histological report of Mass A showed a fibrocollagenous cyst wall that was completely lined by nondysplastic pseudostratified ciliated columnar epithelium; lymphocytic aggregates within the wall, skeletal muscle, and a few nerve trunks in other areas were all noted. A diagnosis of brachial cleft cyst was made.

The histological report of Mass B revealed a fibrocollagenous cyst wall lined by non-dysplastic stratified squamous and respiratory epithelium; congested vascular channels, adipocytes, and lymphocytic infiltrates were all noted. Diagnosis of Thyroglossal duct cyst (TGDC) was made.

Figure 4A (Red arrow): Excised Mass A

Figure 4B (Blue arrow): Excised Mass B

Figure 4: Specimen of the masses A and B removed and sent for histology.

Schneiderian epithelium H&E x 10

Stratified squamous epithelium H&E x 10

Schneiderian epithelium H&E x 40
Figure 5A: Photomicrograph of tissue A

Stratified squamous epithelium H&E x 40.
Figure 5B: Photomicrograph of tissue B

Figure 6A

Figure 6B
Figure 6: Post-operative pictures of the patient (1-week post-op)

Discussion

The coexistence of a **thyroglossal duct cyst** and a **branchial cleft cyst** within the same patient is exceedingly rare, with only a few documented cases in the literature.¹⁻⁷ These two anomalies occur exclusively; however, there are few reportable cases of synchronous occurrence of these two anomalies in one patient.¹⁻⁷ During embryogenesis, the thyroglossal duct develops as a tract descending from the foramen caecum at the base of the tongue to the thyroid gland during the 3rd week of gestation.^{2,4,5} By the eighth (8th) to tenth (10th) week, normal involution of this duct occurs; failure of complete obliteration of this tract results in a TGDC.^{2,4,5} Conversely, BCCs result from incomplete obliteration of the branchial apparatus, most often the second branchial cleft.¹⁻⁷ The simultaneous occurrence of both lesions suggests a possible **common embryological predisposition** or disruption in the development of midline and lateral neck structures during gestation.

Thyroglossal duct cysts can be found anywhere in the neck between the foramen cecum, the base of the tongue, and the suprasternal fissure.^{2,4,6,8} The commonest site of its occurrence is at the level of the thyrohyoid (60.9%).^{2,5,9} Others include the suprahyoid (24.1%), supra-sternal (12.9%), and intra-lingual (2.1%).^{2,5,6,8}

About 2/3 of patients with congenital anomalies of the thyroglossal duct are diagnosed before the age of 30 years, and more than half of these patients are identified before the age of 10 years.^{4,9} This is in consonance with our index patient, who presented with TGDC that was noticed since birth but diagnosed at the age of 22.

Typically, TGDCs present as a painless midline anterior neck swelling that moves with both deglutition and protrusion of the tongue.^{5,6} This is in contrast with thyroid swelling, which moves with deglutition only.^{4,6} Our patient presented with an anterior neck swelling that moves with deglutition but not with protrusion and is more on the left anterolateral aspect of the neck. This made us consider a diagnosis of a thyroid cyst preoperatively. Thyroglossal duct cysts may occasionally present with either a secondary infection, cutaneous fistula, cellulitis, or an abscess.⁵ In this index patient, we aspirated about 5 ml of pus from the TGDC. The fistula formation to either the skin or foramen caecum may occur spontaneously or as a sequel to surgery, trauma, or infection.⁵ No evidence of fistula formation in our patient. Thyroglossal duct cysts may be associated with obstructive symptoms like

dyspnoea, dysphonia, and/or dysphagia.⁶ Our patient did not present with any of these symptoms, possibly due to the relative size and position of the cyst to the upper aerodigestive tract. Thyroglossal duct cysts may sometimes present with non-classical symptoms.⁶ Our patient did not present with the classical symptoms of TGDCs, probably due to the simultaneous occurrence of the branchial cleft cyst along with the TGDCs.

Ultrasound scan (USS) of the neck is the cheapest radiological investigation to confirm the diagnosis of TGDCs, which may reveal the neck lesions as either anechoic or homogeneously hypoechoic with intralesional septa, which may appear pseudo-solid due to possible protein contents, or may appear heterogeneous.⁴ Some of the disadvantages of USS of the neck in the diagnosis of TGDCs are that it does not give reliable delineation of hyoid and infrahyoid TGDCs and cannot reliably measure the base of the tongue in a suprahyoid cyst.⁶ This could possibly explain why the USS of the neck we requested in our index patient did not pick up TGDC, although the cyst was very small relative to the branchial cleft cyst size. Other diagnostic investigations that can be done to diagnose TGDCs include computed tomography (CT), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), thyroglossal fistulography, and fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC).^{2,5} A CT scan or an MRI scan of the neck may reveal a fluid-filled cyst and will outline its size and anatomic relationships as well as the characteristic thick wall of the TGDC.⁷

In this patient, the FNAC of the neck mass revealed a hypocellular smear showing few epithelial cells along with numerous siderophages in a hemorrhagic background with no malignant cells present.

Histologically, the epithelial lining of a TGDC ranges from squamous epithelium to pseudostratified ciliated columnar epithelium with occasional findings of salivary gland or thyroid gland tissue in the wall of the cyst.⁴ In this index patient, the histology of the cyst revealed a fibrocollagenous cyst wall lined by non-dysplastic stratified squamous and respiratory epithelium, congested vascular channels, adipocytes, and lymphocytic infiltrates.

The definitive treatment of TGDC is total excision of the cyst via Sistrunk's operation, which entails resection of the central portion of the hyoid bone along with the cyst all the way up to its attachment to the foramen caecum.^{2,4,10} In the case of our patient, the TGDC was excised via Coller's incision

simply because the diagnosis of TGDC was not entertained preoperatively; however, total excision of the mass was done down to its attachment.

Branchial cleft cyst is the second cause of congenital neck anomalies.¹⁻⁷ They are commonly seen in older children and young adults.^{2,7} In this index patient, the branchial cleft cyst was noticed since after birth but diagnosed at the age of 22 years. Most cases of branchial cleft cysts present as a unilateral neck mass,⁷ similar to the findings in our patient. However, bilateral presentation of branchial cleft cysts is seen in about 2.3% of the cases and is usually familial.² The aetiopathogenesis of branchial cleft cysts is controversial; however, four (4) main theories of origin have been postulated, which include incomplete obliteration of branchial mucosa, persistence of vestiges of the pre-cervical sinus, thymo-pharyngeal ductal origin, and cystic lymph node origin.^{7,10,11}

Branchial cleft cysts usually present as a painless swelling in the lateral aspect of the neck; however, they may present with a painful neck swelling when infected.² They may present anywhere from the submandibular space to the supraclavicular fossa along the course of the second branchial tract and navigate between the internal and external carotid arteries to enter the pharynx at the level of the tonsillar fossa.² They have been classified into 4 subtypes:²

Type I—Most superficial, lying along the anterior surface of the sternocleidomastoid deep to the platysma, but not in contact with the carotid sheath.

Type II—The most common type, where the branchial cleft cyst lies anterior to the sternocleidomastoid muscle, posterior to the submandibular gland, and adjacent and lateral to the carotid sheath.

Type III—Extends medially between the bifurcation of the internal and external carotid arteries, lateral to the pharyngeal wall.

Type IV—lies deep to the carotid sheath within the pharyngeal mucosal space and opens into the pharynx.²

Neck USS is very essential in making the diagnosis of branchial cleft cyst even though it has some limitations compared to CT and MRI.² Neck USS of the mass in this index patient revealed findings in keeping with a brachial cleft cyst. A CT scan or an MRI scan of the neck may reveal a fluid-filled cyst and will outline its size and anatomic relationships as well as the characteristic thick wall of the branchial cleft cyst.⁷

Magnetic Resonance Imaging of the neck is superior to other imaging modalities in assessing deeper soft tissue involvement.¹ On axial views of a CT scan or MRI of the neck, a “beak sign” may occasionally be seen, which represents a curved rim of tissue pointing medially between the internal and external carotid arteries and is pathognomonic of Bailey’s type 3 cyst.²

Histologically, a branchial cleft cyst may be lined by stratified squamous epithelium, but sometimes it is lined by pseudostratified, columnar, and ciliated epithelium.⁷ In this index patient, the histology report of the branchial cleft cyst showed a fibrocollagenous cyst wall that was completely lined by nondysplastic pseudostratified ciliated columnar epithelium, lymphocytic aggregates within the wall, skeletal muscle, and a few nerve trunks in other areas.

Definitive treatment for a branchial cleft cyst is complete surgical excision of the cyst along with its tract.^{1-4,7}

Conclusion

The commonest congenital neck lesions are Thyroglossal duct cysts, followed by branchial cleft cysts. Each of these can occur separately, but synchronous occurrence of the two congenital neck cysts is very rare. They both present as painless neck swelling but could be painful when infected. Complete surgical excision is the mainstay of treatment. There is a need for further research on the possible aetiopathogenesis of the simultaneous occurrence of these two congenital neck cysts.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

Author’s contribution

Substantial contributions: All authors have contributed.

Drafting the work: All authors have contributed.

Final approval: All authors have agreed to publish this manuscript.

Accountability: All authors have agreed to be held accountable for the work’s integrity.

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